

TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING OF STUDENTS IN MEDICAL EDUCATION THROUGH MODELING TECHNOLOGIES OF BIOLOGICAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract: Developing modern medical technologies using effective methods of information modeling. Providing young talents and medical professionals with the knowledge of the role of Information Technology in Medicine, initially applied for medical modeling, and staying updated on innovations in this field.

Keywords: nanotechnological, Algorithms, genetic, epidemics, formula, genders, AI (artificial intelligence), clinical, simulate diagnoses.

INRODUCTION

The fields of medicine and education have been advancing, and it is possible to observe the scientific and technological achievements of representatives in these areas. Whether we have reached the pinnacle of human knowledge or if there is still higher progress awaiting us remains to be seen. Perhaps, with contemporary tools like statistical analyses, algorithms bringing forth new discoveries, and the time for curing diseases approaching! Planning for the future is guided by the foundation of human thinking, surpassing ancient times. Information and technologies have developed significantly to contribute to modeling and planning. Since the last century, medical factors have been modeled through computers, leading to unprecedented discoveries. The advent of computers and technologies allowed the transformation of current events into mathematical symbols and the gathering of vast amounts of medical-biological information through current systems. From nanotechnological medical devices to complex surgeries, biological modeling using medical-technological methods has played a crucial role. Let's explore the importance of biomedical modeling in medical technology and how beneficial these concepts are for students through specific examples.

MAIN PART

"Since ancient times, numerous people have died due to various epidemics and diseases. During that time, there were significant challenges in the field of medicine. It required a lot of time to determine the frequency of occurrence of

infectious diseases in a particular region and to calculate the factors causing them. If the disease was severe, it demanded numerous procedures, time, and even sacrifices. These issues remained a serious concern for experts in the field of medical science. Biological problems like these naturally impeded the progress of future doctors. However, as science and technology advanced, the technology of modeling disease details emerged. In the early 20th century, English and German scientists Hardy and Weinberg created formulas to calculate changes in genotypic populations using mathematical formulas and calculations. Consequently, it became possible to collect necessary information related to diseases, such as the number of affected genotypes in a specific area or the percentage of occurrence in a particular gender or the effectiveness of fighting against it. However, due to the inability of humans to comprehend all the details, research lacked precision.

At the same time, with the help of computer technology and artificial intelligence (AI), all disease details could be learned and treatment options could be found in a short amount of time. Artificial intelligence quickly analyzes disease-related information and models treatment options, providing recommendations. Additionally, by fully utilizing the Microsoft program available on all computers called Mc-Excel, it becomes possible not only to keep an organized record of patient lists and disease cards but also to accurately perform rare calculations related to the quantities of medical pharmaceuticals. Therefore, the demands of the present time urge doctors to work attentively and to adapt to the practical use of modern technologies.

From the aforementioned observations, it is evident that technologies have created several significant opportunities for humanity. These modeling technologies can optimize clinical research, enhance safety for healthcare professionals, ensure proper management of hospital resources, and improve the quality of diagnosis and treatment. Why shouldn't we take advantage of them and shape the future generation with these innovations?"

Research conducted by educators at the Fergana Institute of Public Health shows that monitoring hereditary changes within a population and statistical analysis can be achieved more effectively through technology. "We reached the control of genetic changes within the population using this method," say the researchers. Observations indicate that technology develops on its own, calculates precisely, and provides better diagnostics. To put facts into

perspective, artificial intelligence can now offer a more accurate diagnosis four times better than a human in general health conditions.

The process of introducing students to the "Goldenprog" program of Fergana Medical Institute of Public Health

The development of medical modeling technologies poses a significant task globally—training competent professionals by delivering these innovations to students in the field. The primary goal of teaching such methods to students is to provide them with knowledge of medical technologies and expose them to the possibilities of medical advancements. The Fergana Institute of Public Health's research results, conducted by a group of students under the leadership of S. Ataxanov and Professor M.Qoraboyev, have led to the creation of the "GoldenProg" program. This program measures health indicators in percentages, providing users with a tool to monitor their health. The software analyzes data such as height, weight, pulse, and other 10 parameters. The program diagnoses users, predicts the likelihood of diseases, assesses risk levels, and compiles statistics. These students have successfully proven the effectiveness of the program in providing users with an accurate analysis of their health status, as well as addressing emerging health issues and challenges.

CONCLUSION

The aforementioned modeling programs collect information and simulate diagnoses based on that information. The system monitors public health within defined borders. Thus, acquainting medical personnel with scientific and technological knowledge in the medical field, teaching students deeply about

medical modeling technologies, and introducing changes in medical education can potentially address numerous issues in the history of medical science. Should future doctors, especially students, refrain from using medical modeling technologies? Why shouldn't we teach them the directions for developing these sciences in the rapidly advancing world of science and technology?

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